

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF GENDER AFFILIATION

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Annotation in this thesis, the concept of “linguistic features of gender affiliation” is first explored as an object of linguistics in a communicative environment. The importance of gender affiliation in choosing a social role in society is highlighted.

Key words: gender affiliation, social stratification, social role, reality, gender nature, dialectical principle, interpersonal relationships, linguistic activity, communication behavior, positional situation, anthropolinguistic phenomenon.

In the study of language phenomena in a communicative, dynamic aspect, scientists began to pay attention to the psychophysiological and socio-stratification (gender, age, level of education, etc.) aspects of the language carrier.⁵³ In particular, gender affiliation implies the choice of a social role in society. Usually, gender differences begin after the child is born. For example, it is customary all over the world to buy blue clothes for a boy and pink clothes for a girl. From the age of one or two, there is a difference in the approaches of girls and boys to hairstyles and other customs.

“Gender and gender identity should not be confused. Gender affiliation is a system of masculine and feminine character traits. It is the sum of society's assumptions about how a person should behave, what character traits he or she should have, and so on.⁵⁴” These characteristics are not limited to gender, of course. A person's position in society, interpersonal relationships reflect the characteristics of a complex system of a number of socio-psychological factors, such as his age, gender, occupation, place of residence, marital status.

“Reality is reflected differently at all levels of the language system, at different stages of linguistic activity. The linguistic reflection of reality is not only the experience of a person expressed in language, but also the expression of his personality in the process of communication. Each person's participation in the communication process depends on

⁵³ Горошко Е.И. Говорящий пол (Квантитативные исследования в лингвистической гендерологии) 2003.// <http://www.genderstudies.info/lingvo>

⁵⁴ <https://onona.online/psihologiya/identichnost#i-7>

his or her social status, role, and position.⁵⁵ The principles of the use of language units in the communication system of language carriers, the characteristics of communicative behavior are formed in the context of their social status, including gender.

As a result of the expansion of anthropocentric theories, there is a growing interest in the study of gender features of speech activity in Uzbek linguistics, especially in the field of comparative-typological linguistics.⁵⁶

*As the Ummatali washed himself from the ditch and put on his belt, he began to talk **calmly** to his wife, who was staring at the street door.*

"Don not look too much." Your idiot does not come. He will not be here for five or ten days, rest assured. His wife looked him immediately.

*"Wow, **if I didn't die**, did the police take him?" Did you just sit and watch?*

*"No, no," said Ummatali **calmly**. Nothing happened. Your son is healthy. He is busy with trivial work. He only kidnapped Akbarali's sister in a wedding dress.*

*"**Wow it is shame, wow it is shame!**"*

*The Ummatali, who had come on top of his wife, **who was slapping her on both knees**, came down to calm her. (Said Ahmad "Horizon")*

In general, composure, calm acceptance of reality is characteristic of men. A gesture to speak *calmly* served to express the calm nature of an experienced adult male. Women, on the other hand, tend to hide their relatively sensitive, emotional feelings. The use of emotional urges in a woman's speech, such as *"Wow it is shame, wow it is shame"*, *"slapping her knees"* reflects the gender nature of an ordinary adult rural woman.

Most young women who stay at home have a "inability to restrain the tongue" defect. In the speech of such women, dissatisfaction with the social environment, negative attitudes are often expressed. This can lead to a variety of unpleasant positional situations, of course. Such a position is characterized by the fact that the idle time is sufficient, not to engage in an activity that is interesting to him.

"Everyone is living without quarrel!" Why can't you sit still?

*"**Wow**, do I just sit quietly when our child is insulted?"*

"Do you have a child only? The child fights on his own and recovers on his own..."

"What do I do if the adults insult him?"

- Who? My parents? They want our child to be polite. They do not fight on their own.

⁵⁵ Сафаров Ш. Прагматингвистика. Монография. Т.: 2008 – Б. 157

⁵⁶ Гулямова Ш.К. Ўзбек тили эвфемизмларининг гендер хусусиятлари. Филол. фан. бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) дисс. автореф. Бухоро: 2020.; Юнусова З.З. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида "хурмат" концептининг гендер хусусиятлари // *Замонавий таълим // Современное образование* 2016, 11.; Жўрабоев Б. Немис ва ўзбек тилшунослигида гендер тадқиқи // <https://cyberleninka.ru>; Тўхтасинов И.М. Таржимон тайёрлашда касбий компетенцияларни эквивалентлик ҳодисаси асосида ривожлантириш. Пед. фанл. докт. (DSc) дисс. автореф. Т.: 2018.; Исаева М. Нутққа хос баъзи эвфемик бирликларнинг гендер хусусиятлари // *Ўзбек тилшунослиги: тараққиёт тамойиллари, илмий муаммолар, истиқболдаги вазифалар* Т.: ЎзМУ 2013. –Б. 77-80 ва бошқ.

"Be on their side, too." All good, one I am bad! No day for me here! Who is always bad - I'm bad! ..With that, she will not be silent. (From the Internet)

In this situation, the gender affiliation + family affiliation, that is the upbringing of the bride in another family, the inability to harmonize her behavior with the environment of the bride's family, leads to a social disproportion.

However, good natured, intelligent women can control themselves in negative situations and do not scream emotionally. In this case, the characteristics of gender affiliation + intellectuals belong to the categories of affiliation, the woman normalizes her behavior, finds the willpower to control herself, achieves social affiliation.

- Is there a person who is not so proud?! My brother, like his friends, wants to have a child and have successors.

" I also told your brother several times to "divorce" me. But he does not want to hear about it, he does not even let me talk, "Khadija said, trying to hide her tears.

"Don't make me laugh, Khadijah, if you had told my brother that, he would have already married a woman who would give birth to a son!" Who knows if you have been enchanted him.

"That's enough!"Why are you talking to her, what fault does she do?! Said sighed deeply. "Sister, I can't have children, your daughter-in-law is healthy, it's all up to me ... And your daughter-in-law, whom you always consider guilty, has taken all the blame and has been living as an" innocent culprit "for many years, sister!" said Said, his voice trembling and silent. Said sat down in a chair.

It was clear to them what had happened to the sisters after that. Their face did not turn to say a word. Her face could not bear to look in Khadija. (From the Internet)

In conclusion, the study of any anthropolinguistic phenomenon requires its study on the basis of a two-sided, that is, positive-negative dialectical principle. This allows the observation and study of genderolinguistic phenomena from different angles.

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